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Exposure assessment of bisphenol A, S and F in a Norwegian cohort using physiologically based pharmacokinetic modeling and diet exposure model

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ABSTRACT

Within the EuroMix project, a Norwegian biomonitoring study was conducted to determine aggregated exposure to chemicals present in foods and PCPs in Norway. Several bisphenols (PBs) were investigated and measured in the urines of the participants over 24 hours. Questionnaires, including food diaries, were also collected. This biomonitoring study showed the wide exposure of the cohort to bisphenol A, and to a lesser extent to bisphenol S. For bisphenol F, it was quantified in very few urine samples. In this work, we aimed at assessing the exposure of the Norwegian cohort to the three bisphenols using two approaches. First, we back-calculated the exposure from the urine concentrations using a physiologically based pharmacokinetic (PBPK) model. The second approach calculated the exposure using food diaries filled in by the participants and BPs concentrations in foods measured in several European countries. The first approach was applied to the three bisphenols, and the second one to BPA only. The results showed that similar exposures (within a 2-factor) were obtained in both cases.

INTRODUCTION

The main objective of the H2020 project EuroMix is to develop a tiered, mechanism-based test strategy for refining the risk assessment of combined exposure to multiple chemical using in-silico and in-vitro tools. These strategies include advanced tools for exposure assessment, such as physiological based pharmacokinetic/toxicokinetic (PBPK/PBTK) models to facilitate in-vitro to in-vivo extrapolation (IVIVE) and to estimate internal doses from the different external exposure routes. The toolbox developed in EuroMix will assist regulatory agencies in assessing the risk of exposure to mixtures of chemicals. The Norwegian biomonitoring (BM) study performed within the EuroMix project aims to determine real-life exposure to chemical mixtures from different routes. The BM was conducted to determine aggregated exposure to chemicals present in foods and PCPs in Norway using 24-hour urines. To adjust for temporal variability within a day, collection of 24-hour urine is preferred over spot urines (Aylward et al., 2017). PCPs can be used on a daily basis, and it is believed that exposure to chemicals present in PCPs add to the overall burden of exposure. However, real-life exposure estimates to chemicals from PCPs is mostly lacking (Craig and Ziv-Gal, 2018).

Several bisphenols (PBs) were investigated due to their uses in various consumer products. Bisphenol A (BPA) is used as a monomer of polycarbonate plastic, epoxy resins and in thermal paper (Russo et al., 2017), and human exposure from consumer products therefore occurs, partly through migration into foods and PCPs. Due to restrictions on the use of BPA, bisphenol analogues, such as bisphenol S (BPS), bisphenol F (BPF), bisphenol B (BPB) and bisphenol AF (BPAF), are being used as substitutes for BPA in some consumer products. It has been shown that the exposure to some of these analogous is increasing (Skledar and Masic, 2016).

The present report provides the exposure assessment to BPs of the Norwegian cohort using two approaches. First, we will back-calculate the exposure from the urine concentrations using a physiologically based pharmacokinetic (PBPK) model. The second approach will calculate the

exposure using food diaries filled in by the participants and BPs concentrations in foods measured in several European countries.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study population and design

The human biomonitoring study (EuroMix study) was established at the Norwegian Institute of Public Health (NIPH), and is described elsewhere (Husøy et al., submitted). In brief, participants were recruited among employees from governmental institutes and authorities, and universities in the counties Oslo and Akershus in Norway between September 2016 and November 2017. The recording and sampling period consisted of two non-consecutive 24-hour intervals, with 2-3 weeks between the two sampling periods. The study included 144 participants (44 males age 25-72 years and 100 females age 24-72 years) that completed day one, but only 140 (43 males and 97 females) of these participants completed the full 2-day collections. During the two sampling periods, the participants were asked to fill in a diary of weighed food record, a cosmetic diary, a food frequency questionnaire (FFQ) (only on the first day) and a questionnaire for socio-demographic and lifestyle characteristics (only first day). A 24-hour weighed food record was developed specifically for this project. The recorded consumption from the weighed food diaries and FFQ were further registered and coded by a dietician into the food and nutrient calculation system (KBS) at the University of Oslo (UiO). The cosmetic diary recorded the use of all personal care products (PCP) used during the 24-hours for both days, including the time of use and brand names of the products. Personal information, such as gender, education, age, height, weight, smoking habits, consumption of tap water, visits to swimming pool, skin types of hands (dry, normal, greasy) and number of child births were recorded in the personal questionnaire (Table 1).

All urine was collected during the recording period and blood samples were taken at the end of the 24h period. The participant collected every urine void during the period in separate

containers and marked the containers with time and date. The next day, the samples were immediately stored individually, as pools of urine representing three time periods (6:00-12:00, 12:00-18:00 and 18:00-6:00 the next day). Urinary pools of 30 ml in total were prepared from the samples for given time periods adjusted for volume, as described below:

$$\text{Volume taken from individual sample for pooled sample (ml)} = \frac{\text{Volume of individual sample of urine (ml)} / \text{Total urine volume for time period (ml)} \times 30\text{ml}}{}$$

Out of 144 participants, 8 and 10 subjects did deliver incomplete 24-hour urine collection, for day 1 and 2, respectively.

The study was approved by the Regional Committees for Medical and Health Research Ethics (REK ID no 2015/1868) and all the participants provided their written informed consent.

Table 1. Demographic characteristics of the participants in the EuroMix BM study

Basic characteristics		Males (n=44)	Females (n=100)
Age (years, mean \pm SD)		43.4 \pm 11.7	42.2 \pm 12.3
Weight (kg, mean \pm SD)		82.0 \pm 8.5	65.2 \pm 8.9
Height (m, mean \pm SD)		1.81 \pm 0.06	1.68 \pm 0.06
BMI (kg/m ² , mean \pm SD)		25.0 \pm 2.34	22.8 \pm 3.78
Smoking status (n)	Non-smokers	26	64
	Previous smoking	11	24
	Occasional smokers	7	12
Education (n)	University/college up to 4 years	8	22
	University/college > 4 years	36	78
Women with children (n)	No children	-	45
	1 child	-	19
	2 children	-	26
	3-4 children	-	10

Chemical analyses

Bisphenols were determined using on-line solid phase extraction (SPE) prior to ultra-high performance liquid chromatography (UPLC) coupled to tandem mass spectrometry (MS-MS). Three bisphenols (BPA, BPS, and BPF) were included in the method, as described elsewhere (Sakhi et al., 2018) (Table 2). In brief, labelled internal standards and enzyme solution (beta-glucuronidase/sulfatase in ammonium acetate buffer, pH 5.0) were added to 200 μ L of the sample. After 4 h, 40% formic acid were added to stop the enzymatic reaction. Then, the samples were centrifuged and 80 μ L of the supernatant was injected into the UPLC-MS-MS system. The ionization of the analytes was performed in an electrospray source in negative mode. A signal to noise (S/N) ratio of 10 was considered as limit of quantification (LOQ). The LOD (S/N ratio of 3) was calculated from the respective LOQs and varied from 0.02–0.10 ng/mL (Table 2). The accuracy of the method ranged from 75% to 120%. In-house pooled urine samples and standard reference material from National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) were analysed along with the samples, and the precision was below 26% for the phenols. The BP measurements are presented in Table 3.

Table 2. Limits of detection (LOD) and quantification (LOQ) of bisphenols determined in urine

Compounds	Abbreviations	LOD	LOQ
Bisphenol A	BPA	0.04	0.10
Bisphenol S	BPS	0.10	0.40
Bisphenol F	BPF	0.07	0.20

Table 3: Bisphenols concentrations (ng/mL) in the urine pools in men (n=44) and women (n=100). The mean, standard deviation, the minimum and maximum are reported.

Compounds and pools	N > LOQ	Men	N > LOQ	Women
Bisphenol A				
Pool 1 (6.00 to 12.00)	40	2.1±1.5 [0.2; 6.0]	96	2.2±2.9 [0.1; 22.7]
Pool 2 (12.00 to 18.00)	40	2.2±3.2 [0.1; 15.3]	94	1.7±2.7 [0.1; 22.7]
Pool 3 (18.00 to 6.00)	43	1.6±1.3 [0.1; 6.3]	97	2.1±3.2 [0.1; 22.8]
Bisphenol S				
Pool 1 (6.00 to 12.00)	8	1.1±0.9 [0.2; 2.4]	21	0.7±0.9 [0.2; 4.2]
Pool 2 (12.00 to 18.00)	15	1.0±1.5 [0.1; 15.3]	31	0.4±0.4 [0.1; 1.9]
Pool 3 (18.00 to 6.00)	10	0.6±0.4 [0.1; 1.4]	37	2.5±11.2 [0.1; 68.6]
Bisphenol F				
Pool 1 (6.00 to 12.00)	2	3.1±0.1 [3.0; 3.2]	3	1.9±0.8 [1.1; 2.7]
Pool 2 (12.00 to 18.00)	1	1.9	4	7.2±5.2 [1.8; 14.2]
Pool 3 (18.00 to 6.00)	4	4.8±4.3 [1.6; 10.9]	4	1.8±0.9 [0.6; 2.6]

Exposure assessment using PBPK modelling

The PBPK model

We used the PBPK model in adult women and men for bisphenols A, S, and F developed by Karrer et al. (2018) in the framework of the Euromix project. Karrer et al. (2018) refined a PBPK model, which had been previously developed for BPA in human adults by Yang et al. (2015). The compartments correspond to serum, liver, fat, skin, gonads, brain, richly perfused tissues, slowly perfused tissues, and gut. Compartments are supposed to be homogenous and well mixed, and the distribution of bisphenols is assumed to be flow-limited, i.e. the permeability of the contaminants in the cells of the tissues/organs is much greater than the tissue flow rate. Two routes of exposure are modelled: ingestion and dermal contact. The ingested bisphenols are pre-systemically metabolized in the gut and in the liver. Dermally absorbed

bisphenols enter the skin compartment via the skin surface depot without pre-systemic metabolism. A two-compartment submodule was added for BPA glucuronide (BPA-g) in serum and gut, and a one-compartment submodule for BPA sulfate (BPA-s) in serum. The metabolites enter the serum compartment without being distributed to the other tissues before excretion.

We made several modifications to the PBPK model in order to use it in this study. First the cardiac blood output was adjusted to hematocrit as bisphenol distribution is managed by plasma. Then we added the computation of the urinary concentrations of the bisphenols and metabolites over the three time periods of urine collection. In the initial model, only the cumulative amounts of compounds in urine were computed. A constant rate of excretion of BPA and its metabolites in urine was assumed.

Exposure scenarios

The exposure was assumed to be only by ingestion. This is supported by the study of Karrer et al. (in prep) that estimated a negligible contribution of personal care products to the total aggregated exposure to BPA, BPS and BPF from foods, personal care products (PCPs), thermal paper (TP) and dust. Two scenarios of exposure were tested: i) a constant exposure over the day, and ii) one intake for 30 minutes at the beginning of each period (6h, 12h and 18h). In the second scenario, three intakes over 24 hours were computed and were summed to provide a daily intake.

Reverse dosimetry

Reverse dosimetry simulations were performed to back-calculate the bisphenol diet intakes (DIs) from the measured urinary concentrations. A Bayesian analysis was applied to estimate the oral diet intakes. The Bayes theorem states that the joint posterior distribution of the parameters to be estimated is proportional to the data likelihood multiplied by prior distributions of the parameters. The latter summarizes what is known about parameter values before observing the experimental data (for example, through the literature). The output obtained is a sample of parameter values from their joint posterior distribution. In our study, *a priori* uniform

distribution was assigned to the bisphenol intakes for each participant. The likelihood on the data was assumed to follow a lognormal distribution with 10% of error for all urinary concentrations of metabolites. Measured concentrations below the LOQ were not included in the analyses. Numerical integration methods, Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) methods, were used to estimate the posterior probability distributions. Three independent MCMC chains were run until convergence was reached. MCSim 5.6.6 (Bois and Maszle, 1997) was used to implement the pharmacokinetic model and to perform simulations.

Exposure assessment to BPA using individual diaries

According to Karrer et al. (in prep), for the Norwegian cohort, food was the major source of the aggregated exposure to bisphenols from foods, personal care products (PCPs), thermal paper (TP) and dust. The contribution from PCPs was considered negligible. In this paper, we therefore made a deterministic exposure estimate of BPA from foods only.

The individual food consumption data were used for estimated external dietary exposure. Consumption of the food items were grouped into the same three time periods as described for the pooled urine samples (see section 2.1). In the EuroMix BM study, the consumption of canned and non-canned food was registered, and on average 2.3 % of the foods consumed by the participant were canned.

The concentration data for BPA was taken from the paper by Karrer et al. (in prep), which were based on concentration data in foods from Norway, Denmark, and the French total diet study (TDS), as these were assumed to reflect the exposure for the BM study population best. The mean BPA concentration for each food item from Karrer et al 2019 were allocated to one of the main food categories, bread, grains, cakes, potato, vegetables, fruit and berries, meat, egg, dairy, cheese, butter and oil, sweets, beverages, mixed meal and spice.

Table 3. The BPA concentrations used in the exposure calculations

Food category	BPA conc. (ng/g food)	Food category	BPA conc. (ng/g food)
Vegetables	3.46	Cheese	0.31
FruitBerries	7.78	ButterOil	0.16
Meat	2.10	Sweets	5.16
Fish	5.38	Beverages	0.20
Egg	1.20	Mixed meal	7.69
Dairy	0.18	Spice	33.50

The BPA concentration in canned food is in general higher than for non-canned food, and the BPA measurements in canned foods seemed to dominate in the concentration database. As the consumption of canned foods by BM population were low, the BPA concentrations in canned foods were adjusted according to the average proportion of canned foods eaten by the participants (2.3% of the consumed food), to avoid an overestimation of the BPA exposure. The mean BPA concentration for each food item were thereafter averaged for each food category and multiplied with the gram eaten of the respective food category for each individual, as

$$E_i = \sum_{k=1}^p x_{ik} \left(\frac{(C_{canned} * 0.023)_n + (C_{non-canned})_m}{n + m} \right)_{ik} [ng]$$

with E_i being the external exposure BPA of individual i , x_{ik} the consumption of food category k by individual i , C the BPA concentration in canned and non-canned food averaged over the n number of canned food items and m the number of non-canned food items for each food category k eaten by individual i , and p the number of food categories eaten by each individual i .

RESULTS

Estimates of daily intakes from the biomonitoring data

Constant exposure scenario

The DIs were calculated individually for each woman and man using the PBPK model assuming a constant exposure scenario over the day. Because numerous measurements for BPS and BPF were below the LOQ, it was not possible to estimate a dietary intake for all the participants. Then, only 52 women and 21 men were included for BPS, and 7 women and 5 men for BPF. For each participant, a posterior distribution of the DI was obtained. For all DIs, a coefficient of variation between 8% and 15% was estimated. The distributions of the average individual DI estimates (in ng/kg/d) are represented in Figure 1 for BPA and BPS. Table 4 presents the distribution of the mean individual diet intakes (DI in $\mu\text{g}/\text{day}$) estimated for a continuous exposure to bisphenols over a day. The population seems less exposed to BPS than BPA (between a 2- and a 3-factor). No comparison is possible for BPF due to the low number of participants for which a DI estimate was calculated. We observed that the estimates are rather similar between men and women. For BPS, the mean and standard deviation are a bit higher than for women due to a very high estimate for one woman (55 $\mu\text{g}/\text{day}$). If that participant is not included, the mean and standard deviation would have been $1.1 \pm 1.1 \mu\text{g}/\text{day}$ that is similar to men estimates.

Figure 2 shows the goodness of fit of the model to the measured urine concentrations of total BPA, BPS and BPF. The DIs estimates were used as input of the PBPK model to compute the corresponding urinary concentrations. The model predictions and the measured concentrations are then compared to assess the quality of adjustment of the model (Figure 2) All predictions (except one) fall into the 5-fold error interval. We observed that the variations are greater for BPA. This is explained by the fact that for BPA, most of participants had measured concentrations for the three urine pools whereas for BPS and BPF only one or sometimes two

measurements were available. The estimation of the continuous daily intake was driven then by several data in case of BPA.

Figure 1. Boxplots of the distributions of the average individual DI estimates (in ng/kg/d) for BPA and BPS in women and men.

Table 4. Distribution of the mean individual diet intakes of BPA, BPS and BPF ($\mu\text{g}/\text{day}$) under the continuous exposure scenario. N indicates the number of participants for which it was possible to reconstruct the exposure.

Compound	N	Mean \pm SD	P5	P25	P50	P75	P95
Bisphenol A							
Women	100	3.3 \pm 2.6	0.9	1.5	2.4	4.1	8.8
Men	44	3.3 \pm 2.8	1.0	1.7	2.5	3.3	9.1
Bisphenol S							
Women	52	2.0 \pm 6.9	0.3	0.5	0.8	1.3	4.0
Men	21	1.2 \pm 1.8	0.2	0.4	0.6	1.4	2.4
Bisphenol F							
Women	7	4.5 \pm 3.2	1.1	2.7	3.2	6.1	9.1
Men	5	5.9 \pm 3.5	3.1	4.4	4.7	5.8	10.7

Figure 2. Comparison of the model predictions of urinary concentrations with the measured concentrations of total BPA, BPS, and BPF in women and men for the constant exposure scenario. The plain line is the perfect correspondence between the predictions and the experimental data, and the dashed lines represent the 5-fold error interval.

Exposure scenario with 3 diet intakes

The DIs for BPA were calculated individually for each woman and man using the PBPK model assuming an exposure scenario of three diet intakes at the beginning of each time period (6:00, 12:00 and 18:00). At least one measurement in urine was available for each participant, so the DIs were calculated for the whole cohort. Table 5 and Figure 3 present the distributions of the average of the individual DIs (in $\mu\text{g}/\text{d}$). For all DIs, a coefficient of variation between 12% and 20% was estimated. Figure 4 shows the goodness of fit of the model to the measured urine concentrations of total BPA. All predictions are very close to the measured concentrations.

Table 5. Distribution of the mean individual diet intakes of BPA ($\mu\text{g}/\text{day}$) in women and men for the 3-intake exposure scenario. N indicates the number of participants for which it was possible to reconstruct the exposure.

	N	Mean \pm SD	P5	P25	P50	P75	P95
Women							
Pool 1 (6 to 12)	96	1.3 \pm 1.4	0.2	0.4	0.9	1.5	4.2
Pool 2 (12 to 18)	94	0.8 \pm 0.9	0.1	0.3	0.5	0.9	1.9
Pool 3 (18 to 6)	97	1.7 \pm 2.0	0.3	0.7	1.2	1.8	3.3
Total – 24h	100	3.5 \pm 3.2	0.6	1.6	2.6	4.4	10.2
Men							
Pool 1 (6 to 12)	40	1.1 \pm 1.3	0.2	0.5	0.8	1.2	2.5
Pool 2 (12 to 18)	40	1.3 \pm 3.1	0.1	0.2	0.5	0.9	4.3
Pool 3 (18 to 6)	43	1.2 \pm 1.0	0.2	0.7	1.1	1.5	2.5
Total – 24h	44	3.4 \pm 3.9	0.6	1.6	2.2	3.3	9.1

Figure 3. Boxplots of the distributions of the average individual DI estimates (in $\mu\text{g/d}$) for BPA in women and men when the 3-intake scenario is considered. The DI were computed for each pool period, and over the day (sum of the three pools).

Figure 4. Comparison of the model estimates with the measured urinary concentrations of total BPA in women and men when the 3-intake scenario is assumed. The plain line is the perfect correspondence between the predictions and the experimental data, and the dashed lines represent the 5-fold error interval.

Estimates of daily intakes from the diet diaries

Table 5 shows the estimated dietary exposure to BPA from each time period for male and female participants of the EuroMix BM study of study day 1. The mean BPA exposure was in the same range for males and females and ranged from 1.98 – 2.30 μg and 1.47 -2.16 μg for the different time periods for males and females, respectively. The BPA exposure for the time periods 6:00 – 12:00 and 12:00 – 18:00 were higher than for the time period 18:00 – 6:00, with the exception of males at the 75 and 95 percentiles. This indicate that the males eat more foods later in the day, than the females.

Table 6. Estimated dietary exposure of BPA (μg) for meals from each time period.

Time period of meals	Gender	Mean	P5	P25	P50	P75	P95
6:00 – 12:00	F	2.10	0.27	1.02	1.73	2.86	5.00
	M	1.98	0.23	0.59	1.96	2.58	4.47
12:00–18:00	F	2.16	0.19	1.02	1.84	2.91	5.57
	M	2.30	0.11	0.70	2.07	3.27	6.31
18:00 – 6:00	F	1.47	0.07	0.27	1.00	2.09	4.52
	M	2.25	0.06	0.42	1.81	2.99	6.23

The foods contributing the most to the BPA exposure were fruit and berries, grain, vegetables, fish and beverages (Figure 3). The BPA concentration in the food categories vegetables (n = 5 food items), fruit and berries (n = 4 food items) and fish (n = 13 food items) was mainly from canned food, while the BPA measurement contributing most to the BPA concertation in grains (n = 5 food items) were from cooked pasta. Some of the food items had repeated measurements, but the means were used in the exposure estimates.

Figure 5. Estimated BPA exposure (ng) from the major food categories for participants in the EuroMix BM study from day 1.

DISCUSSION

In this deliverable, we aimed at assessing the diet exposure to BPA, BPS and BPF on the Norwegian cohort using two approaches: one starting from the measured concentration in urine, and one starting from the information on food consumption collected through diaries. Both approaches were applied to BPA as numerous data are available for this compound compared to its analogs. Indeed, the second approach based on food diaries was not applied to BPS and BPF as data on food contamination by these compounds are still missing. Moreover, the reverse dosimetry approach with the 3 intakes per day was not applied to BPS and BPF due to numerous samples under the LOQ.

For BPA, the daily intakes computed with the two approaches are compared in Table 7. We can observe that the both scenarios used for reverse dosimetry lead to similar diet DI on average. The more realistic scenario with 3 intakes allows to deal with the variations in intake over the day. Such variations have an impact on the internal exposure of the individuals. The estimates

obtained with the food diaries are a bit higher (about a 2-factor) compared to the ones obtained from the biomarkers (urine concentrations) but are still in the same ranges.

Table 7. Daily diet intakes estimates ($\mu\text{g}/\text{d}$) for BPA by reverse dosimetry with two scenarios, a constant exposure (sc 1) or 3 diet intakes (sc 2), and food dairies (sc 3)

		Sc 1	Sc 2	Sc 3
Women	100	3.3	3.5	5.7
Men	44	3.3	3.4	6.5

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